

PEDAGOGICAL MODEL OF DEVELOPMENT OF ARTISTIC AND AESTHETIC COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MUSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS BASED ON INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION

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Abstract. *The purpose of the program for students of a higher educational institution is to strengthen high spiritual qualities in young people, which are considered the main criteria of maturity, to study the necessity of spirituality in the life of an individual, society and state based on social and moral criteria, to teach young people the concept of high spirituality. It is necessary to explain that moral highness is a factor that ensures the stability of the country, and to scientifically justify that high morale is an invincible force and the main criterion for the development of society. Based on this goal, we can set the following goal for music education experts - it is necessary to use the opportunities of music education sciences to train competent experts.*

This article presents an innovative model of developing the artistic-aesthetic competence of future music education teachers by forming the integration of social and humanitarian sciences with music teaching disciplines in higher music education, establishing interdisciplinary cooperation, and its analysis.

Keywords: *music, artistic-aesthetic, competence, method.*

Introduction

Today, the idea of building a new society based on modern ideas related to the sustainable development of our country is supported by all layers of our people and it is important that our country unites around this idea. In this process, "we look with great confidence to Zayali in building a new Uzbekistan and creating the foundations of the Third Renaissance. Therefore, it is necessary to consider it as our primary task to support scientific and creative researches in every way, to create the necessary conditions for them. For this purpose, specific measures are being developed and implemented by our government" [1; 42]. On the basis of these measures, educational reforms are being carried out rapidly. Therefore, the system of higher education in our country has entered a new stage of its development and is characterized by the active implementation of reforms and the search for productive principles and models of training specialists. This process is recognized by certain ideas in pedagogical education, which are related to the general laws of the development of modern society.

Literature analysis and methodology

Interdisciplinary integration also expands the individual capabilities of disciplines. For example, it is a one-sided and wrong idea to study music sciences only on the basis of a certain subject, to think that it is possible to develop the artistic and aesthetic competence of future music education teachers only by using the opportunities of this category of subjects. On the contrary, the sciences of this category are closely related to all sciences, especially social, concrete and

natural sciences. Famous pedagogue V.A. Sukhomlinsky emphasizes the organic interaction and interdependence between different fields and forms of education, and believes that the most important thing in this process is the problem of harmonizing pedagogical effects [2; 129]. The essence of this problem, which represents one of the most important laws of education, - he said, - is the following: the pedagogical effectiveness of each means of influencing a person depends on how well thought out, goal-oriented, and effective the other means of influence are. Any influence on a person is null and void unless there are hundreds of other influences.

In order to study the possibilities of developing the artistic-aesthetic competence of future music education teachers by integrating the subjects of the subjects of music education, the undergraduate educational direction "Artology" was determined as a research object. In particular, the subjects "Philosophy" in the block "Natural-scientific and humanitarian sciences", "General pedagogy" in the block "General professional sciences", and "Teaching technology of educational science" in the block "Elective sciences" of the curriculum of this educational direction on the basis of ensuring the integration of students, an experimental education on the development of artistic and aesthetic competence of future music education teachers was carried out.

Pedagogical scientist M.T. Davletshin, in his views on the pedagogic professionogram, shows that it is necessary for the future teacher to have the following qualities:

- personal qualities: love of children, hard work, active in public affairs, etc.
- possession of professional knowledge: understanding the essence of the educational process and its goals and tasks, etc.
- characteristics specific to one's profession: acquisition of methodological knowledge of modern pedagogy, etc.
- personal pedagogical resourcefulness: the ability to choose the necessary materials for training, the ability to plan goals, etc. This pedagogical professionogram corresponds to various specialties of pedagogical educational institutions, and it turns out that these qualities are very important in the development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future teachers of music education.

Results. In modeling the process of developing the artistic and aesthetic competence of future music education teachers, the reforms implemented in our country and their results, scientific and technical achievements, the innovations and developments being created, the growth of the intellectual potential of young people, the developing state, society and individual it is necessary to be based on the modern requirements that are changing, updating and developing day by day depending on the needs and developments.

It was concluded that the development of artistic and aesthetic competence of future music education teachers should be implemented on the basis of the following principles: professionalism and competence, integrity and systematicity, activity orientation.

The multifunctional field of social education is based on the following principles:

- consistency - aimed at revealing the integrity of the object and the mechanisms that ensure it, determining the various relationships of the complex object and bringing them to a single example;
- integrity - reflects the internal unity of the object, its relative autonomy, independence from the environment;

- subjectivity - includes consideration of the student from the point of view of the ability to set and adjust goals, to be aware of motives, to independently implement actions and assess their compliance with the plan, to make life plans;

- integration - ensures integration of irregular events, parts, elements into a whole (orderly and structural).

In addition, the methodology of interdisciplinary cooperation forms the following skills in future music education teachers, which direct them to the creation of a creative product:

- emotional-image qualities: inspiration, emotional excitement in creative situations, imagery, imagination, fantasy, dreaminess, romanticism, sense of novelty, creative imagination;

- initiative, inventiveness, readiness to invent, originality, non-standard;

- ability to generate ideas;

- acquisition of diversity of opinions, compatibility with moral norms in the family, higher educational institution, social environment;

- the ability to conduct a conversation with the studied object, the ability to choose learning methods, the ability to determine the structure and content, the ability to determine the relationship between the objects of approach.

Discussion. In the modeling of the pedagogical system aimed at developing the artistic and aesthetic competence of future music education teachers, the following functions were considered:

- methodological support function. The implementation of this function is related to the regulatory and legal documents and the social order that defines the theoretical foundations of the development of artistic and aesthetic knowledge and skills of future music teachers;

- function of regulatory and legal support. This function requires determining the principles, content, tasks, pedagogical conditions, and diagnostic tools for involving future music teachers in activities related to the development of artistic and aesthetic knowledge and skills;

- methodological support function. It requires clarifying the methodological (content, form, methods and tools) conditions for the development of artistic and aesthetic knowledge and skills of future music teachers;

- practical-applied (empirical) function.

This function allows solving a number of tasks: formation of value-oriented principles and stable motives in connection with the development of artistic and aesthetic knowledge and skills of future music teachers, analysis of the researched process and making certain corrections; evaluation and analysis of results, etc.

The goal-oriented block plays a leading role for other blocks of the system of development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future music education teachers. Based on the clarification of the content of this block, the educational standard and social order, regulatory and legal bases in the field of research were determined. The goals and objectives of the model were also clarified.

The development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future music education teachers as a social order, the Strategy of Actions for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law "On Education", the State Education Standard of higher education, as well as , was determined by the normative-legal documents of the development of moral culture.

In the process of developing a model aimed at developing artistic and aesthetic competence in future music education teachers, the following tasks were considered:

- 1) clarification of methodological approaches to the development of a model for the development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future music education teachers;

- 2) clarification of the block structure of the model;
- 3) reveal the relationship between the model block and its elements;
- 4) to describe the block structure and elements of the model.

The above-mentioned goals and tasks of developing artistic and aesthetic competence in future music education teachers are related to complex methodological approaches. The object of study of the methodological approach is interpreted as a strict methodological direction of research from the point of view of the principle of guiding the general strategy of research.

Effective approaches to the development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future music education teachers can include:

- the systematic-process approach is characterized by setting a problem that reflects the logic of scientific research as the general basis of research, clarifying the main and local goals, clarifying conflicting opinions and points of view, and art in future music education teachers. - ensures the development of the aesthetic competence development model;

- axiological and reflexive approaches, as the theoretical-methodological basis of the strategy, determine the directions of theoretical research, reflect its general view. These approaches make it possible to determine the value system and provide feedback in the system of developing artistic and aesthetic competence in future music education teachers;

- a personal-activity-oriented approach to determine the mechanism and procedures for organizing the activities of professors and teachers and students, to reveal the peculiarities of the practical use of the studied phenomenon in order to achieve the set goal. appears as a directed tactic.

The next block of the model reflects the result. This block performs an evaluative function and reflects the practical aspect of the research. Therefore, it reflects the levels, criteria and indicators of the development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future music education teachers. Four evaluation criteria were considered in the study: 1) cognitive; 2) concerning activity; 3) personal; 4) axiological.

The following requirements were met when determining the evaluation criteria: the number of criteria should not be less than three, each criterion should have at least three indicators;

Criteria are measured on the basis of indicators that can be concluded about the level of their low or high manifestation;

1) the criteria should be adopted on the basis of taking into account the main types of pedagogical activity as much as possible.

The analysis of modern literature on the issue shows that the main measurement criteria reflect the fact that a person has a higher level of development. The following three measurement criteria were determined in the study: 1) cognitive; 2) concerning activity; 3) axiological.

Summary

In conclusion, the effectiveness of the development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future music education teachers is determined by the presence of certain quality changes.

1. The proposed program for diagnosing the level of development of artistic-aesthetic competence in future music education teachers was tested at the foundation stage and used in the process of educational experience-testing, which allows to determine the level of development.

2. The development of artistic-aesthetic competence synthesizes the artistic-aesthetic taste and understanding of future teachers, qualitative and quantitative characteristics: the norm of mastering the high ethical-aesthetic values of an individual student in society; the level of

development of all elements, needs, abilities and ideals of the student's moral-aesthetic consciousness; it will be known that they represent the standard of implementation in all spheres of life.

3. In modeling the process of developing the artistic and aesthetic competence of future music education teachers, the reforms implemented in our country and their results, scientific and technical achievements, the innovations and developments being created, the growth of the intellectual potential of young people, a developing state, society and based on the modern requirements that are changing, updating and developing day by day depending on the needs of the individual, developments.

4. The principle of systematicity, scientificity and continuity in music education and training should be organized on a scientific basis in each training with its structure and content. The scope of knowledge about music is the main factor of music education and upbringing. It reflects the rules, conclusions, and generalized musical experiences of music created by mankind.

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